

Analysis of Studies on Physical Education and Game Lessons in Türkiye Between 2019-2024

Türkiye’de 2019-2024 Yılları Arasında Beden Eğitimi ve Oyun Dersi Kapsamında Yapılan Çalışmaların Analizi

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Abstract

Physical education and game lesson is one of the compulsory subjects taught by class teachers in grades 1, 2, and 3 for 5 class hours and in grade 4 for 2 class hours. With the lowering of the starting age for school in 2012, the importance of play in child development has been emphasized, and the Physical Education lesson has been changed to Physical Education and Game Activities, with an increase in class hours. This subject was renamed as Physical Education and Game in 2018 and is still one of the subjects with the highest number of class hours in the primary school curriculum. This research aims to examine articles and theses on physical education and game lessons. Descriptive content analysis technique was used in this study, and the universe of the study consists of articles, master's theses, and doctoral dissertations in this field. Purposeful sampling method was used for sampling, and the sample of the study consists of a total of 36 studies reached in the searches with the keywords of physical education and game lesson in YÖK Thesis, Google Scholar, and Dergipark databases. It was found that 14 of these studies were articles, 3 were doctoral dissertations, and 19 were master's theses. According to the findings of the research; it is observed that the most studies were conducted in 2022, and out of these studies, 5 were master's theses, 1 was a doctoral dissertation, and 4 were articles. It was determined that the majority of the studies were in the field of educational sciences (55.6%), and master's theses constituted the majority. It is observed that the studies were mostly conducted using quantitative and qualitative methods. Surveys and scales were mostly utilized in the studies. In conclusion, it is observed that there are few studies in this field, and the quantity at the doctoral level is also noteworthy. It is believed that experimental studies conducted by physical education and sports teachers will greatly contribute to the field.

Keywords Primary School, Curriculum, Physical Education and Game Lesson

ÖZ

Beden eğitimi ve oyun dersi, ilkököl 1,2 ve 3. sınıflarda 5 ders saati, 4. Sınıflarda 2 ders saati şeklinde sınıf öğretmenlerinin yürüttüğü zorunlu derslerden biridir. 2012 yılında okula başlama yaşının aşağıya çekilmesiyle birlikte oyunun çocuğun gelişimi üzerindeki etkisi önemsenmiş ve Beden Eğitimi dersi, Oyun ve Fiziki Etkinlikler dersi olarak değiştirilmiş ayrıca ders saatleri de artırılmıştır. Bu ders 2018 yılında isim değişikliği ile Beden Eğitimi ve Oyun adını almış günümüzde halen ilkököl müfredatında en çok ders saati olan derslerden biri olarak okutulmaktadır. Bu araştırma ile, Beden eğitimi ve oyun dersi üzerine yapılan makale ve tezlerin incelenmesi amaçlanmıştır. Betimsel içerik analizi tekniği kullanılan bu çalışmanın evrenini bu alanda yapılan makaleler, yüksek lisans ve doktora tezleri oluşturmaktadır. Örneklem yöntemlerinden amaçlı örneklem yöntemi kullanılmış ve araştırmanın örneklemini YÖK Tez, Google Akademik ve Dergi park veri tabanlarında beden eğitimi ve oyun dersi anahtar kelimesi ile yapılan aramada ulaşılan toplam 36 çalışma oluşturmaktadır. Bu çalışmaların 14'ünü makale, 3'ünü doktora tezi ve 19'unu yüksek lisans tezlerinin oluşturduğu tespit edilmiştir. Araştırmanın bulgularına göre; en fazla çalışmanın 2022 yılında yapıldığı ve bu çalışmaların 5 tanesinin yüksek lisans tezi, 1 tanesinin doktora tezi ve 4 tanesinin makale olduğu görülmektedir. En fazla çalışmanın eğitim bilimleri alanında (%55,6) olduğu ve yüksek lisans tezlerinin oluşturduğu tespit edilmiştir. Çalışmaların daha çok nicel ve nitel yöntemler kullanılarak yapıldığı görülmektedir. Çalışmalarda en çok anket ve ölçeklerden yararlanılmıştır. Sonuç olarak bu alanda az sayıda çalışmanın olduğu görülmüş ve doktora seviyesinde de bu nicelik dikkate değerdir. Beden eğitimi ve spor öğretmenlerinin uygulayıcı olduğu deneysel çalışmaların da yapılmasının alana büyük katkı sağlayacağı düşünülmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: İlkokul, Program, Beden Eğitimi ve Oyun Dersi

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Introduction

In Türkiye, primary education is compulsory for 4 years. During these four years, students are required to attend 30 hours of classes each week. The Ministry of National Education's Board of Education and Discipline (TTKB) determines weekly lesson hours and communicates them to the relevant institutions. The subject of research, Physical Education and Games, is among the compulsory courses in primary schools. With the implementation of the 12-year (4+4+4) compulsory education system in 2012, the Physical Education course was renamed as Games and Physical Activities, and in a subsequent change in 2018, it was renamed back to Physical Education and Games. This course is taught by classroom teachers in primary schools.

The objectives of Turkish National Education are outlined in the Basic Law of National Education, which was adopted in 1973. In the second purpose of this law, it is emphasized that children should develop a healthy and balanced character and personality in moral, physical, mental, and spiritual aspects; and that they should be raised as individuals who possess scientific thinking, are free, respectful of human rights, aware of social responsibility, and are creative and productive. The Physical Education and Games course has been included in the curriculum with the aim of contributing to students' healthy and balanced growth in moral, mental, physical, and spiritual aspects. The curriculum for this course aims to develop students' fundamental movement skills, active and healthy living strategies, concepts, and related life skills that they will use throughout their lives, thereby preparing them for the next level of education (Ministry of National Education, 2018).

The rapid spread of technology and the increasing amount of time children spend with technological devices from a young age have made it necessary to implement activities in schools to meet the need for physical activity. Arslan (2008) emphasizes that with the intense integration of technology into our lives, rapid urbanization, and the stress brought about by living conditions, sports and physical education activities should become a habit. He states that the most appropriate age group for acquiring this habit is primary school students. Memiş and Yıldırım (2006) also express that if habits of playing and engaging in sports are not established during primary school through physical education classes, individuals will inevitably face difficulties in utilizing their leisure time and participating in healthy activities as they grow older.

In primary schools, one of the courses offered to develop students' skills, in addition to academic subjects, is Physical Education and Games. In this course, students not only engage in physical activities but also have the opportunity to socialize by developing the habit of playing together. Dalaman and Korkmaz (2010) state that adopting an active lifestyle through games at school significantly enhances the physical skills of children aged 6 to 12 and contributes to their social development. Playing and moving freely is a child's most natural right; therefore, schools should organize activities that encourage children to learn through play in free environments rather than depriving them of this right. Özşaker and Orkun (2005) express that physical education and sports classes are a vital component of general education, ensuring children's rights to move freely and play. This situation contributes to children's development both physically and mentally, and allows them to enjoy sports activities.

Petray (1989) emphasizes that physical education classes have distinct goals, such as ensuring students maintain their physical fitness throughout their lives and developing healthy activity habits. The National Association for Sport and Physical Education (NASPE) defines the primary aim of the course as helping students increase their physical activity levels throughout their lives and fostering positive attitudes

(National Association for Sport and Physical Education, 1995). Dalaman (2010) states that physical education is a crucial complement to general education and also contributes to a child's personality development.

Additionally, it is emphasized that this course plays a significant role in helping students develop a happy, morally upright, healthy and balanced personality both individually and socially; be productive and constructive and acquire the values of national culture and the behaviors required for democratic living. Humphries and Ashy (2000) and O'Sullivan (1996) state that classroom teachers with well-structured experiences in teaching physical education understand the importance of the subject and develop a positive attitude toward it.

According to the weekly lesson schedule published by the TTKB in 2018, a total of 30 lesson hours is required in primary schools each week. The Physical Education and Games course is included as a compulsory subject for 5 hours per week in the first three grades and 2 hours in the fourth grade (Board of Education and Discipline, 2018). When we look at the proportion of mandatory lesson hours for this course, it accounts for 16.6% of the total lesson hours in the first three grades and 6.66% in the fourth grade. Additionally, the use of Physical Activity Cards (PAC) and the "I Am Playing" Compilation Booklet is recommended for teachers and students, alongside the course content. This course is structured around two learning areas and six sub-learning areas (Ministry of National Education, 2018).

The main aim of this study is to identify articles related to the Physical Education and Games course taught in primary schools, published between 2019 and 2024 in Dergi Park and Google Scholar, as well as open-access theses available in the Higher Education Council Thesis Center, and to examine them through various parameters. In this context, the following research questions have been addressed:

How is the distribution of theses and articles on primary school physical education during the 2019-2024 period in terms of years, publication venues, and publication types?

How is the distribution shaped according to the research methods used?

What is the status of distribution based on data collection methods?

The study covers the years 2019-2024, which is related to the fundamental changes brought about by the 4+4+4 segmented compulsory education system implemented in 2012. During this period, significant changes were made to the course name and curriculum, weekly lesson hours were increased, and additional resources were provided to teachers. Furthermore, the name of the course was changed in 2018. For these reasons, examining the developments during the specified years is important.

Method

This research is a descriptive survey model that analyzes studies related to the Physical Education and Games course in primary schools. For data analysis, categorical analysis and frequency analysis, which are techniques within content analysis, have been used. Content analysis is a technique aimed at systematically organizing and summarizing similar data around specific concepts and themes in a way that is understandable to the reader (Büyüköztürk et al., 2009; Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2008).

The population of the research consists of journals containing articles related to the primary school physical education course available on Dergi Park and Google Scholar, as well as open-access theses (master's and doctoral) in the Higher Education Council Thesis Center in Türkiye. The research sample was created using a purposive sampling method and includes articles published on Dergi Park and Google Scholar, as well as

theses related to the primary school physical education course in the Higher Education Council Thesis Center, from 2019 to 2024. The study is limited to Dergi Park, Google Scholar, and the YÖK Thesis Center, which is accessible electronically. As a result of the examinations conducted within this scope, 22 works (19 master's theses and 3 doctoral theses) and 14 articles related to the primary school physical education course were identified.

Research Model

This research is a descriptive survey model that analyzes studies related to the Physical Education and Games course in primary schools. For data analysis, categorical analysis and frequency analysis, which are techniques within content analysis, have been preferred. Content analysis is defined as a systematic method aimed at organizing and summarizing similar data around specific concepts and themes in a way that is understandable to the reader (Büyüköztürk et al., 2009; Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2008).

Universe-Sample (Sampling or Participants)

The population of the research consists of journals containing articles related to the primary school physical education course available on Dergi Park and Google Scholar, as well as open-access theses (master's and doctoral) in the Higher Education Council Thesis Center in Türkiye. The research sample has been determined using a purposive sampling method and includes articles published on Dergi Park and Google Scholar, as well as theses related to the primary school physical education course in the Higher Education Council Thesis Center, from 2019 to 2024.

Data Collection Tools

During the research process, 19 master's theses, 3 doctoral theses, and 14 articles were examined. A Publication Classification Form was used to evaluate these theses and articles. The publication classification form developed by Çiltaş et al. (2012) for mathematics education was reorganized by researchers for the purpose of this study. The sections of the publication classification form were filled with information obtained from the contents of the theses and articles. The data obtained from the studies examined within the scope of the research were collected in the publication classification forms and presented as percentage and frequency values.

Data Collection

In this section, the data collection processes used in the research and the application part of the study should be explained in detail. The explanations should present the positive and negative developments that occurred during the process and how these processes were managed to the reader.

Before the study, the publications within the scope of the research were identified by the researcher, and a work plan was created. To ensure the reliability of the study, approximately 20% of the works were randomly selected using a cross-checking method, and the information related to these works was re-examined to ensure consistency. The formula used for reliability calculation was "Reliability = Agreement / (Disagreement + Agreement)," and the reliability coefficient of the research was determined to be 0.87 (Miles and Huberman, 1994).

Analysis of Data

During the research process, a total of 19 master's theses, 3 doctoral theses, and 14 articles were examined. A Publication Classification Form was used to evaluate these theses and articles. The publication classification form developed by Çiltaş and

colleagues (2012) for mathematics education was reviewed and revised by the researchers for this study. The sections of the publication classification form were filled with information obtained from the contents of the theses and articles. The data obtained from the studies examined within the scope of the research were collected in the publication classification forms and presented as percentage and frequency values.

Result

This research examines a total of 36 works, including 22 theses and 14 articles published between 2019 and 2024 in the YÖK Thesis Center, Dergi Park, and Google Scholar, related to the primary school Physical Education and Games course. The information regarding the type of publications and their publication venues is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of Research by Publication Year and Type of Publication

Years	Thesis	Thesis	Article	f	%
2019	5	1	5	9	25
2020	1	-	1	3	8,4
2021	5	1	5	7	19,5
2022	5	-	5	10	27,7
2023	2	1	2	6	16,6
2024	1	-	-	1	2,8
Total	19	3	14	36	100

Upon examining Table 1, it is noted that a search was conducted using the keywords "physical education and games" on the YÖK Thesis Center, Google Scholar, and Dergi Park websites, with a limitation to the years 2019-2024. A total of 36 works were identified, of which 19 were master's theses, 3 were doctoral theses, and 14 were articles. When looking at the publication year of the studies, it is observed that the highest number of works was conducted in 2022, consisting of 5 master's theses, 1 doctoral thesis, and 4 articles.

Table 2: Distribution of Research by Publication Venue and Type of Publication

Field	Thesis (Master's Degree)	Thesis (Doctorate)	Article	f	%
Physical Education and Sports	8	1	7	16	44,4
Educational Sciences	11	2	7	20	55,6
Total	19	3	14	36	100

Upon examining Table 2, it is noted that 8 of the master's theses and 1 of the doctoral thesis studies within the scope of the research were conducted in the field of physical education and sports, while 11 master's theses and 2 doctoral theses were conducted in the field of educational sciences. Among the articles, 7 were published in the field of physical education and sports, and 7 were published in the field of educational sciences.

Table 3: Distribution of Research by Publication Method

Study Method	Thesis (Master's Degree)	Thesis (Doctorate)	Article	f	%
Quantitative	8	1	6	15	38,9
Qualitative	7	-	8	15	38,9
Mixed	4	2	-	6	22,2
Total	19	3	14	36	100

Upon examining Table 3, it is observed that 15 of the studies were conducted using quantitative methods, 15 using qualitative methods, and 6 using mixed research

methods. It can be seen that both quantitative and qualitative methods were most frequently preferred in the studies.

Table 4: Distributions of Data Collection Methods in Research

Data Collection Tools	Thesis (Master's Degree)	Thesis (Doctorate)	Article	f
Scale/Survey	12	2	4	18
Interview	8	2	6	16
Document	3	1	3	7
Experimental	-	1	1	2
Total	23	6	14	43

When examining Table 4, it can be seen that during the study process, a total of 18 scales/questionnaires, 16 interviews, 2 experimental methods, and 7 document analyses were utilized for data collection. Multiple data collection tools were used in the studies examined.

Discussion And Conclusion

This study examines research conducted on physical education and play classes in primary schools in Türkiye between the years 2019 and 2024. The timeframe is defined because the play and physical activities course was changed to physical education and play class in the 2018-2019 academic year. Studies related to physical education play classes applied in kindergartens and articles produced from the theses examined were excluded from the scope of the research. The majority of the studies (%52,7) consist of master's thesis works.

In this study, it was found that among the publications examined, the highest number of research studies was conducted in 2022 (%27,7), followed by 2021 (%19,5). Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the least research was conducted in 2020 (%8,4). The increasing concern about technology addiction and the understanding of the importance of physical activity in children, along with changes in educational policies specifically related to physical education and play classes, suggest that there has been an overall increase in the number of publications in recent years. Yılmaz and Kurt (2019) identified the years 2012-2018 as a limitation in their study titled "Analysis of Research Conducted on Physical Education and Play Classes in Türkiye," where they found that 96% of studies related to physical education and play classes were conducted in the field of physical education and sports. However, in our analysis covering the years 2019-2024, it was found that the majority of the studies (%55,6) were conducted in the field of educational sciences. This result indicates that there is also significant attention given to studies related to physical education and sports within the field of educational sciences. When examining the research methods used in the studies included in this work, it was observed that the highest proportion of studies (%38,9) utilized quantitative and qualitative research approaches, while %22,2 of the studies were conducted using mixed methods. In the studies examined, the most commonly used tool for data collection was questionnaires (%41,8), while interviews were preferred in %37,2 of the cases.

Suggestions

In our country, classroom teachers conduct physical education and play classes. According to the results of the studies examined, classroom teachers feel inadequate in this subject (Çivril Kara et al., 2022), and the results also indicate that classroom teachers

believe it would be more appropriate for specialist teachers to teach this class (Çıldır, 2021; Boy, 2021; Filiztekin, 2023). Therefore, studies can be conducted in primary schools where physical education and play classes are taught by physical education and sports teachers.

Interdisciplinary studies that relate physical education classes to other subjects can also be conducted.

It is suggested that research be conducted on teachers who can teach this subject at the undergraduate level.

Studies on physical education and play classes encompass the curriculum, teachers, and attitudes. Research can be conducted to measure students' development, attitudes, and competencies.

Kısaltmalar / Abbreviations

SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
n	örneklem sayısı
p	anlamlılık değeri

Beyanlar / Declarations

Etik Onay ve Katılım Onayı / Ethics approval and consent to participate

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During the preparation and writing of this study, the principles of scientific integrity, ethics, and citation, as stipulated in the "Higher Education Institutions Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Directive," were fully observed; no falsification was made on the collected data, and this study has not been submitted to any other academic publication platform for evaluation. The author bears full responsibility for any potential violations regarding the article.

Veri Ve Materyal Erişilebilirliği / Availability of data and material

Bu çalışmanın bulgularını destekleyen veriler, makul talepler üzerine sorumlu yazardan temin edilebilir. Veri seti yalnızca akademik amaçlar için erişilebilir olacak ve verilerin herhangi bir kullanımı, orijinal çalışmayı referans gösterecek ve katılımcıların gizliliğini koruyacaktır.

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. The dataset will be accessible only for academic purposes, and any use of the data will recognize the original study and maintain the confidentiality of the participants.

Çıkar Çatışması / Competing interests

Yazarlar, bu makalede sunulan çalışmayı etkileyebilecek herhangi bir çıkar çatışması veya kişisel ilişkiye sahip olmadıklarını beyan etmektedirler.

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Yazar Katkıları / Authors' Contribution Statement

Araştırma tasarımı: MÇ, EA, HÇ; İstatistiksel analiz: MÇ, EA, HÇ; Makale hazırlığı: MÇ, EA, HÇ; Veri toplama: MÇ tarafından yapılmıştır.

Research design: MÇ, EA, HÇ; Statistical analysis: MÇ, EA, HÇ; Preparation of the article: MÇ, EA, HÇ; Data collection: Conducted by MÇ.

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